

BASIC PROBLEMS THAT STUDENTS FACE WHILE PRODUCING SPEAKING

Turg'unboyeva Shakhnoza

Student of UzSWLU

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Abstract: Nowadays, it is fact that effectively learning English is becoming more and more popular for EFL learners. This is because language plays a leading role in different attitudes between all countries around the world. Choosing the best way for this process is very important for us. Because there are a lot of books, gadgets, and technologies for learning a language, sometimes we do not know which is the most suitable for our position. It can be easily said that speaking is a more essential skill for learners. Even though it is easy to learn, a big part of learners come across some difficulties during improving their speaking ability. So, in this article, it can be mentioned that, some problems which are appeared in our speech, their reasons and some recommendations.

Key words: ability, grammar mistakes, vocabulary, psychology, emotions, first speech.

When we start learning something, we try to find different ways, which are more effective for us. There are a lot of opinions, suggestions, and recommendations about it. So, we know only the speaker can improve it, because it demands working hard, concentrating, avoid all mistakes. We know this productive skill is very necessary for people. It is not impossible to learn it in one day, but when we do it regularly, it takes less time. Additionally, there are some reasons for this problem. Firstly, most speakers have a worry and shyness from the first speech because of their character. It is fact that everyone has individual psychology and personality. If a speaker is an introverted person he or she does not express the full meaning of their idea. Authors of the book "English language teaching methodology" said that this process requires speakers made decisions about why, how, and when to communicate depending on the cultural and social context in which the speaker's action occurs. Also, it involves a dynamic interrelation between speakers and listeners the results in their simultaneous interaction of producing and processing spoken discourse under time constraints. [1; 163]. Furthermore, other speakers want to finish their speech earlier and they try to fast. After that, their speech will become inaccurate and short. Also, it may cause grammatical mistakes in the contest. If students do not have enough grammatical knowledge, it affects in a negative way to their speech.

In that book it is mentioned that the speaker chooses ready words or grammatical units from the memory. Especially, our opinions will be ready when we think in our mother tongue. However, interference is observed. So, memory also plays a big role when we started speaking. Another problem which we came across very often is a lack of vocabulary. Students do not know a lot of words or their synonyms and they lose the order of speech. Then, it appeared a lot of pauses in our speech. Verderber gives his opinion about it in this way: “You want your speech to be clear. That is, you want your audience to have an instant understanding of the words you use. Your speech will become clearer if you will learn to rely on precise, simple, and specific/concrete words and learn to eliminate unnecessary clutter”. [5; 101]

When it comes to our mistakes, firstly, we must confirm what kind of difficulties we have? What is the main problem, how can we solve them, and so on? Many writers and poets give their advice in their way. Also, J. Michael Sproule studied this issue and gave some advice: “If you want to improve your public speaking skills, you are in good company. Thousands of today’s men and women are vitally interested in becoming better able to organize and present ideas. People all over America, at work and in community life, want to speak competently and confidently to groups, both small and large. Worried about giving your first speech? Would you believe that thousands of men and women, who are actively pursuing their careers, envy your chance to take a college course in public speaking? It is true. People in the “real world” need and want competence in public speaking.” [4; 7] The writer’s opinion is true. When people want to improve speechmaking they should speak in public during daily work. Other tips are also helpful, but when we practice it with our friends, colleagues, and in public it will be more effective. Simply, when we need some help, we should try saying it without any shyness or interruption. Maybe, it will be our first step in starting our attractive speech.

To improve our speaking skills, working individually will be also useful. Only we know what we want to say. It does not matter, it is fact or only opinion, we should say it with good intonation. Because each person has individual thoughts, maybe it is not proven, but it is not repeatable. It is more important to think widely because opinion is the biggest component of good speaking. Everyone knows it is easier to learn our mother tongue than other languages.

When it comes to learning English for Central Asian nationalities, like Uzbek may occur some problems as well. Initially, it will be the reason for our location. Our country is far from the American continent and from history, we develop in

different places. Furthermore, our traditions and mentality are also different, they have their traditions, and we have our customs. But after migration and international attitudes, we also learn it easily. It is not difficult to find speakers like American or British speakers in our country. So, it depends on people's motion. We should practice more and more, however, in the correct way. There are some ideas about starting speaking at an early age. It is natural while learning a foreign language that students make mistakes. They make mistakes in auditing when they misunderstand something in a text. They make mistakes in speaking when pupils mispronounce a word, violate the order of words in a sentence, misuse a preposition or an article, use the wrong intonation, etc. The teacher's main aim is to prevent pupils' errors. There is a good rule: "Correct mistakes before they occur." In the other words, careful teaching results incorrect English, and pupils make very few mistakes. However, they make them and the problem is how to correct pupils' errors. Great care in teaching speaking so that the learner could use the spoken forms as accurately as possible, that is, with native-like sentence patterns and pronunciation. For this purpose that student should have some adequate model of speech-preferably in the person of a native or near-native speaker of the language, or the form of a faithfully recorded voice of such a speaker. [2; 21]

Everyone can mention different ways to improve speaking skills. When learners choose the best way and concentrate on it they will achieve result more than expected. Each person has different ideas which are very unusual, however, they cannot express their opinion exactly. So, according to scientists' and philologists' opinions, we should speak accurately. Firstly, we should not avoid from first speech. It is fact that each person has shyness and emotions from the first speech. But we should destroy all barriers and after that, we will take your first step. Also, we do not avoid mistakes. Speakers, especially new learners only think about their mistakes in their speech and do not want to make a speech. However, it does not solve the problem. Furthermore, students should improve their vocabulary by reading many interesting books. We should improve our word base first. When we read books out loud it will be more effective. Through this, we memorize new words and their meanings from the context. So, it is a very important part.

To sum up, if learners work on themselves every day, they will have an excellent outcome in the end. It should be mentioned that speaking is a productive skill, if learners stop speaking in that language, they will lose all results which they get still now. No one is born as an intelligent, all achieve

something by being confident and working hard. So, we should start working intensely from now.

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